

Radical reaction opening of glucosyl 1,2-cyclopropane derivatives : Synthesis of α and β C-glycosides and oxepane derivatives

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α and β C-glycosides and oxepane derivatives are prepared by radical reaction opening of glucosyl 1,2-cyclopropane derivatives. Structures have been confirmed by NOE studies of NMR, FABMS and C-H analysis.

In continuation of the on going research project of carbohydrate chemistry^{1,2}, cyclopropanation reaction on substituted sugar alcohol was studied. During the course of the chemical modification of 1,2-cyclopropane derivatives by ring opening through Barton's deoxygenation method on xanthate, an exomethylene double bond is created at C-2 position in both α and β C-glycosides. The exomethylene generated thereby is a tube handle in functionalization. Thus hydroboration affords an alcohol at C-2 position while epoxidation gives an epoxide that can be used for the creation of tertiary carbon centre on sugar otherwise difficult to achieve. Similarly ozonolysis gives a ketone which on reduction would give C₂-OH while deoxygenation gives a 2-deoxy-C-glycoside. Thus these olefins synthesized in the present study are useful in the preparation of several important and interesting sugars.

At the same time 7 membered oxepane derivative was also formed as a side product during the formation of C-glycosides which is difficult to construct.

Results and discussion

The synthesis of C-glycosides **8** and **11** was initiated from D-glucose. Thus, D-glucose was first converted to tri-*O*-benzyl-D-glucal (**2**) by a known procedure³. Next it was aimed at the conversion of glucal (**2**) into the allylic alcohol (**4**), which is a ring intermediate for the cyclopropanation reaction. In the present study thus the requisite one carbon was introduced by Vilsmyer-Haack reaction⁴. Accordingly the glucal (**2**) on reaction with DMF-POCl₃ at RT gave the corresponding formyl derivative **3** in 70% yield. In the ¹H NMR of **3**, the glucal H-2 was conspicuously absent, while

the CHO proton appeared as a singlet at δ 9.2, while signals due to the rest of the protons appeared at the extended chemical shift (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Reduction of the aldehyde (**3**) with NaBH₄ in methanol afforded the alcohol (**4**) in 80% yield.

Scheme 2

The next target in the synthetic sequence in the preparation of C-allyl glycosides was the introduction of cyclopropane ring system into the allylic alcohol molecules. We adopted the Furukawa modification of Simmons Smith cyclopropanation reaction⁶. Accordingly reaction of **4** with diiodomethane (10 eq) and diethyl zinc (5 eq) in DCM at -20°C gave the both α as well as β cyclopropane **6** and **5** respectively in 1 : 1 ratio in an overall yield of 80% (Scheme 3).

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In the ^1H NMR spectrum of α isomer (**6**), the cyclopropyl protons appeared at δ 0.86–0.97 (m), 0.78–0.86 (m) and 0.72 (t, J 6.5 Hz). In the ^1H NMR of β isomer (**5**), the cyclopropyl protons appeared at δ 1.23–1.34 (m), 1.02–1.08 (m) and 0.72 (t, J 6.52 Hz).

Scheme 3

Compound **6** on reaction with CS_2 and MeI in the presence of NaH in THF gave the xanthate **10** in 85% yield in which S-CH₃ signal appeared as a three proton singlet at δ 2.52 in ^1H NMR spectrum. Similarly β isomer **5** was converted into xanthate **7** in 79% yield, appeared as a three proton singlet at δ 2.55.

The xanthates **10** and **7** were then subjected to radical reaction. Accordingly reaction of **7** with Bu_3SnH in toluene in the presence of catalytic AIBN underwent facile cyclopropane ring opening to afford two products **8** and **9** (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

The structures of these two compounds were unambiguously confirmed on the basis of NOE studies of NMR and spectral analysis. The ^1H NMR of **8** showed the absence of multiplet signals of the cyclopropyl ring hydrogens with the appearance of protons of CH₃ group as a three proton doublet (J 8.27 Hz) at δ 1.4. The olefinic protons appeared as two separate singlets at δ 5.2 and 5.08.

The ^1H NMR of **9** showed the characteristic peaks of olefin protons at δ 5.13 as doublet (J 4.6 Hz). The H₆ protons appeared as two multiplets at δ 2.60–2.79 and at δ 2.11–2.24 as 2H multiplet.

Likewise the cyclopropane ring opening in **10** was also achieved under the above reaction condition to give two products viz. **11** and **9** (Scheme 5).

Scheme 5

Compounds **9** and **11** were characterized on the basis of TLC behaviour and spectral data. In the ^1H NMR, the signals due to cyclopropane ring protons were absent. The olefinic protons appeared as separate singlet at δ 5.31 and 5.10. The methyl protons appeared as 3H doublet at δ 1.45 (J 6.81 Hz).

To determine the structure of **8** and **11**, first homonuclear decoupling experiments were done with **11**. On irradiation of CH₃ doublet at δ 1.39, the H₁ multiplet appeared as doublet at δ 4.58 (J 3.7 Hz). Subsequently on irradiation of H₁, the methyl doublet appeared as singlet at δ 1.34. These experiments showed the presence of -CH-CH₃ group in **11**.

Similarly the homonuclear decoupling experiments were done with **8**. The protons attached to Me group was decoupled and Me came as singlet at δ 1.68. Moreover when methyl group was decoupled the H₁ came as doublet at δ 4.58 (J 6.25 Hz). These two experiments shows the presence of -CH-CH₃ group in **8**.

To illustrate the position of CH₃ group in both **8** and **11**, NOESY correlation experiments were carried out. The results are shown in tabular form.

The important observation is that in case of **11**, the NOE enhancement factor of CH₃ (caused by H₅ proton irradiation) is sufficiently more (10.26%) c.f. that of NOE enhancement factor of CH₃ group in **8** caused by H₃ proton irradiation (9.01%). The NOE has been observed if the distance between the interacting nuclei are ≤ 3.5 Å, which implies that in **11**, CH₃ group is in neighbourhood and specially close to H₅ (α oriented). So CH₃ group in **11** is α oriented. Hence CH₃ in **11** is strongly coupled with H₅ giving rise to high NOE enhancement factor (10.26%).

On the other hand in **8**, H₁ and H_a both nearer to CH₃ group thus coupled to give higher NOE enhancement factors which give rise to the fact that in **8**, CH₃ group is β oriented.

Table 1. NOESY correlation data and report of NOE enhancement factor

Compd.	Irradiating grs/atoms	NOESY correlations	NOE enhancement factor (%)
8 (β isomer)	CH ₃	CH ₃ -H ₁	8.82
		CH ₃ -Ha	14.71
	H ₃	H ₃ -Hb	5.41
		H ₃ -H ₅	4.05
		H ₃ -H ₄	9.91
11 (α isomer)	CH ₃	H ₃ -CH ₃	9.01
		CH ₃ -Ha	2.73
		CH ₃ -H ₁	9.55
		CH ₃ -H ₃	5.91
	H ₅	CH ₃ -H ₅	5.45
		H ₅ -H ₃	7.05
		H ₅ -CH ₃	10.26

Thus with the NOESY correlation we can easily determine that **8** is β isomer and **11** is α isomer.

Experimental

General methods: Optical rotations were measured with JASCO DIP 360 digital polarimeter at 25°C. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on FT (200 Gemini) spectrometer. 2D NMR spectra were recorded on Varian Unity (400 MHz) spectrometer. The spectra were recorded in CDCl₃, chemical shifts are reported in [(δ ppm)] relative to TMS as internal standard, coupling constants (*J*) were expressed in Herz. Elemental analysis were carried out in Elementar Vario EL CHN analyzer. Mass spectra (both MS, FABMS) were recorded on VG Micromass 7070H or Finnigan Mat 1020B mass spectrometer. Ionisation was carried out at 70 eV by electron impact, samples were introduced directly. Thin layer chromatography was done on precoated silica gel 60f 254 (0.5 mm) glass plates.

3,4-Di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-5-pyrancarbaldehyde (3):

Vilsmeier Haack reaction was done with a solution of **2** (5 g, 12 mmol) in 24 ml dry DMF (0°C) added to 3.36 ml (5.534 g, 36 mmol) POCl₃. After successful completion and ether work up, the crude compound was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 15% ethyl acetate-pet. ether) to give pure aldehyde **3** (2.90 g) in 55% yield as a syrup, [α]_D + 6.49° (*c* 0.615, CHCl₃); lit. [α]_D + 6.8° (*c* 0.34, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.30–3.40 (2H, m, C₆H), 3.42 (1H, s, H₁), 4.20–4.36 (8H, m, benzylic CH₂), 7.10–7.20 (16H, m, aromatic H), 9.20 (1H, s, CHO).

3,4-Di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-5-pyranylmethanol (4):

NaBH₄ (0.0224 g, 0.593 mmol) reduction was done with the aldehyde **3** (0.174 g, 0.3954 mmol) in dry methanol (5 ml). After successful completion and work up, the compound was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 25% ethyl acetate-pet. ether) to give **4** (0.197 g) in 90% yield as a syrup [α]_D + 26.99° (*c* 0.715, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.50 (1H, s, OH), 3.60–3.80 (2H, m, H₆), 3.91–4.22 (3H, m, H₃, H₄, H₅), 4.50–4.74 (7H, m, 3 × CH₂Ph), 6.45 (1H, s, H₁), 7.20–7.40 (15H, m, aromatic H) (Found : C, 75.246; H, 6.685. Calcd. for C₂₈H₃₀O₅ : C, 75.311; H, 6.772%).

3,4-Di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl perhydro- α -cyclopropa[b]pyran-4-yl methanol (6) and 3,4-di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethylperhydro- β -cyclopropa[b]pyran-4-yl-methanol (5):

To 2–3 ml DCM solution of diiodomethane (3.447 g, 1.036 ml, 12.8 mmol, cooled at –20°C, diethyl zinc (1 M in hexane, 6.436 ml, 6.436 mmol) was added and stirred for 30 min. Compound **4** (0.568 g, 1.28 mmol) in DCM (5 ml) was added to it. This was kept at –20°C till completion (24 h), after the completion of the reaction, saturated ammonium chloride (10 ml) was added at 0°C, stirred for an hour and extracted with DCM (3 × 10 ml). Organic layer was dried (Na₂SO₄) concentrated, purified by column chromatography (silica gel). First eluted (12% ethyl acetate-pet. ether) was compound **6** (0.264 g) in 45% yield as a syrup. Second eluted (15–16% ethyl acetate-pet. ether) was **5** (0.290 g) in 49% yield as a syrup, [α]_D + 40.85° (*c* 0.64, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **6** : δ 0.72 (t, interaction between H₁ and H₂, *J* 6.52 Hz), 0.78–0.86 (m, interaction between H₁-H₂), 0.86–0.97 (m, interaction between H₁-H₂), 1.299, 1.40 (2H (1+1), both bs, H₃), 2.34 (1H, bs, OH), 3.03 (1H, ABq, *J* 4.34 Hz, H₁), 3.40–3.90 (4H, m, H₅, H₆, H₇), 4.10–4.20 (1H, m, H₄), 4.43–4.80 (6H, m, benzylic CH₂), 7.19–7.39 (15H, m, aromatic H); FABMS for **6** (MNBA as matrix +Na), M⁺+23=483 (Found : C, 75.536; H, 6.968. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₂O₅ (**6**) : C, 75.625; H, 7.004%).

[α]_D + 12.83° (*c* 0.78, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (200 MHz, CDCl₃) for compound **5** : δ 0.72 (t, *J* 6.52 Hz, interaction between H₁-H₂), 1.02–1.08 (m, interaction between H₂-H₂), 1.23–1.34 (m, interaction between H₁-H₂), 1.40 (1H, s, H₃), 1.56 (1H, bs, OH), 3.04 (1H, d, *J* 13.04 Hz, H₁), 3.41–3.48 (2H, m, H₇), 3.52–3.68 (2H, m, H₅, H₆), 4.11–4.20 (1H, m, H₄), 4.50–4.80 (6H, m, benzylic CH₂), 7.14–7.39 (15H, m, aromatic H); FABMS for **5** (MNBA as matrix +Na); M⁺CH₂OH = 429 (Found : C, 75.585; H, 6.906. Calcd. for

$C_{29}H_{32}O_5$ (**5**) : C, 75.625; H, 7.004%).

3,4-Di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethylperhydro- α -cyclopropa[b]pyran-4-yl-[(S-methylthio)thiocarbonyl]methanol (**10**) :

To a solution of compound **6** (0.665 g, 1.445 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml), NaH (0.052 g, 2.168 mmol, 60%) was added portionwise. It was stirred at room temperature for 90 min and cooled to 0°C. CS_2 (0.1318 g, 0.1075 ml, 1.734 mmol) was added and stirred at room temperature for 1 h. Finally the reaction mixture was cooled to 0°C and MeI (0.2463 g, 0.1050 ml, 1.7347 mmol) was added and stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0°C, MeOH was added and excess CS_2 and MeI were evaporated under reduced pressure. It was extracted with ethyl acetate, evaporated and residue was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 10% ethyl acetate-pet. ether) to give **10** (0.716 g) in 90% yield as a syrup, $[\alpha]_D + 21.750$ (*c* 0.91, $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 0.88–1.04 (cyclopropyl protons), 1.42 (1H, s, H_3), 2.52 (3H, s, S- CH_3), 3.39–3.73 (4H, m, H_7, H_6, H_5), 3.86–3.97 (1H, m, H_4), 4.40–4.82 (6H, m, benzylic CH_2), 7.20–7.36 (15H, m, aromatic H); FABMS (MNBA + NaCl); $M^+ + Na = 550 + 23 = 573$ (Found : C, 67.549; H, 6.134. Calcd. for $C_{31}H_{34}O_5S_2$: C, 67.605; H, 6.223%).

3,4-Di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl perhydro- β -cyclopropa[b]pyran-4-yl-O-[(S-methylthio)thiocarbonyl]methanol (**7**) :

A solution of compound **5** (0.225 g, 0.489 mmol) in dry THF was treated with NaH (0.0176 g, 0.733 mmol, 60%) portionwise. It was stirred at room temperature for 90 min and cooled to 0°C. CS_2 (0.0446 g, 0.0363 ml, 0.5869 mmol) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. Finally the reaction mixture was cooled to 0°C and MeI (0.0833 g, 0.0355 ml, 0.5869 mmol) was added. It was stirred at room temperature for 45 min. The reaction mixture was cooled to 0°C, MeOH was added and the excess CS_2 and MeI were evaporated under reduced pressure. This was extracted with ethyl acetate, evaporated and residue was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, 8% ethyl acetate : pet. ether) to give **7** (0.239 g) in 89% yield as a syrup, $[\alpha]_D + 35.6175^\circ$ (*c* 0.48, $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 0.89 (t, *J* 6.97 Hz, interaction between H_1-H_2), 1.14–1.22 (m, interaction between H_2-H_2), 1.28 and 1.46 (2H, both s, H_3), 2.55 (3H, s, S- CH_3), 3.63–3.73 (1H, m, H-1), 3.41–3.48, 3.57–3.64 and 3.99–4.09 (4H, m, H_5, H_6, H_7), 4.15 (1H, d, *J* 4.59 Hz, H_4), 4.45–4.80 (6H, m, benzylic CH_2), 7.11–7.38 (15H, m, aromatic H); FABMS (MNBA + NaCl) : $(M^+ - 1) + Na = 549 + 46 = 595$ (Found : C, 67.537 ; H, 6.174. Calcd. for $C_{31}H_{34}O_5S_2$: C, 67.605;

H, 6.223%).

3,4-Di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl-6- α -methyl-5-methyltetrahydro-2H-pyran (**11**) and *3,4-di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl-5-methylene oxepane* (**9**) :

A solution of **10** (0.153 g, 0.278 mmol) in dry toluene (5 ml) was treated with tributyltin hydride (0.161 g, 0.149 ml, 0.556 mmol) and cat. AIBN. This was kept under reflux for 30 min under N_2 atmosphere. After the completion of the reaction, toluene was concentrated under reduced pressure. It was extracted with ether, washed with saturated KF solution. Ether layer was concentrated and purified by column chromatography. First eluted (6% ethyl acetate-pet. ether) was **11** (0.059 g) in 44% yield as a syrup. Second eluted (7% ethyl acetate : pet. ether) was compound **9** (0.057 g) in 48% yield as a syrup. $[\alpha]_D$ of **11** – 3.62° (*c* 0.515, $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) for compound **11** : δ 1.40 (3H, d, *J* 8.27 Hz, CH_3), 3.46–3.79 (4H, m, $H_4, H_5, 2 \times H_6$), 3.82–3.919 (1H, m, H-1), 4.26 (1H, d, *J* 9.19 Hz, H_3), 4.44–4.84 (5H, m, benzylic CH_2), 5.08 (1H, s, H_{2a}), 5.20 (1H, s, H_{2b}), 7.11–7.40 (15H, m, aromatic H); FABMS of compound **11** : (MNBA + NaCl) $(M + Na)^+ = 467$ (Found : C, 78.258 ; H, 7.187. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{32}O_4$ (**11**) : C, 78.347; H, 7.256%).

$[\alpha]_D$ of compound **9** + 20.10° (*c* 0.62, $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR (200 MHz, $CDCl_3$) for compound **9** : δ 2.11–2.24 (0.5H, m, H_6), 2.60–2.79 (m, 0.5 \times 2H, H_6), 3.38–3.63 (4H, m, 2 \times H_8, H_2, H_3), 4.04 (1H, d, *J* 3.72 Hz, H_4), 4.06–4.20 (1H, m, H_7), 4.25–4.64 (6H, m, benzylic CH_2), 5.13 (2H, d, *J* 4.59 Hz, $5_{2a}, 5_{2b}$), 7.08–7.39 (5H, m, aromatic H); FABMS for compound **9** (MNBA + NaCl); $[M + Na]^+ = 444 + 23 = 467$ (Found : C, 78.326; H, 7.209. Calcd. for $C_{29}H_{32}O_4$: C, 78.347; H, 7.256%).

3,4-Di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl-6- β -methyl-5-methylenetetrahydro-2H-pyran (**8**) and *3,4-di(benzyloxy)-2-benzyloxymethyl-5-methylene oxepane* (**9**) :

Compound **7** (0.081 g, 0.14727 mmol) was taken in dry toluene (5 ml), tributyltinhydride (0.0856 g, 0.0791 ml, 0.2945 mmol) and catalytic AIBN (added portionwise) were added dropwise to the reaction mixture. It was allowed to reflux under N_2 atmosphere for 45 min. After the completion of the reaction, toluene was concentrated under reduced pressure. It was extracted with ether and washed with saturated KF solution, organic layer was concentrated and the residue was purified by column chromatography. First eluted (silica gel, 5% ethyl acetate : pet. ether) was **8** (0.030 g) in 47% yield as a syrup and second eluted (silica gel, 7% ethyl acetate : pet. ether) was **9** (0.033 g) in 51% yield as a syrup, $[\alpha]_D$ of **8** + 11.42° (*c* 0.56, $CHCl_3$); 1H NMR (200 MHz,

CDCl₃) for compound **8** : δ 1.45 (3H, d, J 6.81 Hz, CH₃), 3.42–3.78 (4H, m, H₄, H₅, 2×H₆), 3.92 (1H, q, J 4.59 Hz, H-1), 4.08 (1H, d, J 9.19 Hz, H₃), 4.47–4.91 (6H, m, benzylic CH₂), 5.10 (1H, s, H_{2b}), 5.31 (1H, s, H_{2a}), 7.11–7.46 (15H, m, aromatic H); FABMS (MNBA + NaCl) of compound **8** : (i) (M + H)⁺ = 445; (ii) (M⁺–91) = 353 (Found : C, 78.295; H, 7.178. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₂O₄ : C, 78.347; H, 7.256%).

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